

Research Article

Literary Criticism : Prominence and Progressivness

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Abstract

The present article is intended to study deeply about literary criticism with the title "Literary Criticism: The Provenance, Prominence and progress". Precisely, criticism is the systematic study of merits and demerits and literary criticism keenly studies; evaluates and gives layers of interpretations and embedded connotations from all genres of literature, which is truly a challenging task, unless one is very through with literatures of the world, one can not at all properly criticise or evaluate, therefore, literary criticism is the considered to be the toughest genre. And this article differentiates the slight nuances among literary criticism, literary theory, principle, laws and hypothesis and clearly paves the path for the enthusiastic readers in specific, beginners in general who have inclination towards literary criticism to dig deeper and deeper and gives the catalogue of a few important writings, which have shaped the history of literary criticism indeed.

Keywords: Literary criticism, enigmatic, evaluation and literary genre, procedural interpretation

Introduction

While literary criticism is the interpretation and evaluation of literatures, literary theory is a plausible hypothesis. One most focusing note is to know about 'theory' is a plausible hypothesis that is supported by a considerable amount of evidence; experimentation, which is likely to be true. Some of the scientific theories are Evolution theory ; Big Bang Theory . The most notable literary theories are poststructuralist theory ; Marxist theory ; Feminist Theory ; postmodern theory and post colonial theory. Thus, a theory is a plausible hypothesis that is supported by a considerable amount of evidence, while a principle is a scientific law that has been proved beyond reasonable doubt. There is a difference between a law and a principle. A law describes an event, but it does not explain why the event happens. Laws describe relationships, specific situations, and conditions. This is different from a principle, which tells us why and how things happen. Principles are ideas based on scientific rules and laws that are generally accepted by scientists. They are fundamental truths that are the foundation for other studies. The principles are very qualitative. The Principles of Relativity; the Principle of Special Relativity. The laws are different from the principle. Newton's law of gravitational attraction describes how objects are influenced by gravity. If you drop an apple, it will fall. If you throw an apple in the air, it will follow a specific path while falling down. Newton's laws don't tell us why the apple falls or what causes it to fall, just that it does fall. A hypothesis is usually tentative; it is an assumption or suggestion made strictly for the objective of being tested.

What criticism means really ?

From the experience of profound and wide study, the diverse and uncountable works of literature can be appropriately criticised. It is worth and timely to mention Alexander Pope's *An Essay on Criticism*, which clearly outlines how to criticise, One of the lines of easy is " little learning is a dangerous thing; Drink deep, or taste not the Pierian spring"1. (P. 200) Without a comprehensive and holistic approach to literature, one's criticism can not be appropriate. To criticise the body of literature, one should dive deep into literature. The Johns Hopkins Guide to Literary Theory and Criticism makes no distinction between literary theory and literary criticism, and almost always uses the terms together to describe the same concept. However some critics consider literary criticism a practical application of literary theory, because criticism always deals directly with particular literary works, while theory may be more general or abstract.

The history of literary criticism

It is very interesting to know that It surprisingly dates back to Aristotle in 4th century BC, who had written a master piece, titled, *poetics*; another seminal work is *Natya Shastra* on ancient Indian literature and Sanskrit drama . And the medieval criticism often focused on the religious texts and the several long religious traditions of hermeneutical and textual exegesis have had a profound influence on the study of secular texts. The Medieval Arabic literature and Arabic poetry from the 9th century , one of the most notable personality is Al-Jahiz in his all-Bayan wa-'l-tabyin and al-Hayawan.. The Baroque criticism is a sort of criticism, baroque means ornate or flowery , the imitation of classical literature and all the principles have been inherited from the classical antiquity, which denotes a style of European architecture, music, and art of the 17th and 18th centuries that followed mannerism and is clearly characterised by the ornate details. In architecture the period is exemplified by the palace of Versailles and by the work of Wren in England. Major composers include Vivaldi, Bach, and Handel ; Caravaggio and Rubens are the very important baroque artists. Samuel Johnson is one of the one of the most influential writers and critics of the 18th century. The late nineteenth century brought forth renown to authors known more for their literary criticism than for their own literary work such as Mathew Arnold.

Another important kind of criticism is 'The New Criticism', which includes 'Russian Formalism'. Which is also slightly present in Britain and in the United States. 'Reader Response' criticism is another form of criticism, which is the most famous one focusing on the response of the readers. Northrop Frye published the influential *Anatomy of Criticism* in 1957, a theory which has discussed the major issues critically. And Ferdinand de Saussure's theories of linguistics are very influential in developing the structural approach to literary criticism. In fact, we understand by the observation that 'Literary theory' was greatly influenced by structuralism and post-structuralism and other kinds of continental philosophy. Feminist criticism in the history has concentrated on the problems of females and there are four notable feminist- waves so far, which have raised many issues that have been confronted by women in the history. Elain Showalter, Simon de Beauvoir, Virginia Woolf and many others. "The function of criticism is not limited to an apparently reluctant revelation of the significance of what has been wrought by the creative artist" 2 (P. V111) .

The major schools of 20th century and the important texts

The major schools of critical analysis are New Historicism; structuralism; post-structuralism deconstructionism ; post-modernism ; Marxist literary criticism ; cultural studies

and ecocriticism; queer theory and disability studies. Some of the important of texts of literary criticism to refer are Plato's Republic; Horace's Art of poetry; Longinus's On the Sublime; Boethius's The Consolation of Philosophy; Valmiki's Invention of Poetry; Anandavardhana's Light on Suggestion; Francis Bacon's The Advancement of Learning; John Dryden's An Essay on Dramatic Poesy; Joseph Addison's On the Pleasures of the Imagination; Samuel Johnson 's Preface to Shakespeare ; Thomas Carlyle's Symbols; John Stuart Mill's What is Poetry ?; Emile Zola's The Experimental Novel; Leo Tolstoy's What is Art ? ; Ferdinand de Saussure's Course in General Linguistics; T. S Eliot's Tradition and the Individual Talent; Simon de Beauvoir; Michel Foucault's What is an Author?; Elaine Showalter's Toward a Feminist Poetics; M. H Abrahams's How to Do Things with Texts. One of the most prominent works in literary theory is 'Deconstruction' in 1967 is by the French philosopher , Jacques Derrida, a philosophical movement that vividly questions the traditional assumptions about certainty and truth and it always tries to demonstrate how statements about any text subvert their own meanings. The first book in which Derrida explains about deconstruction is Of Grammatology, which was written in 1967.

The prominent themes and terms

Critical study leads readers to understand the hidden connotations, symbols, metaphors and myths. "When we study something, we use our minds to acquire knowledge of the thing that we study. There are several, indeed, countless ways of studying something; and the reluctant knowledge changes according to our methods of acquiring knowledge, our ways of studying" 3 (P. 3)

Intentional fallacy is a term used in 20th century literary criticism to describe the problem inherent in trying to judge a work of art by assuming the intent or purpose of the artist who created it. It was introduced by W. K Wimsatt, and Monroe C. Beardsley in The Verbal Icon, which was written 1954. 'Russian Formalism' is an influential school of literary criticism in Russia from the 1910s to the 1930s. It has made a great impact on Mikhail Bakhtin and on structuralism as a whole. The movement's members are widely considered the founders of modern literary criticism. The next one is 'Ideological State Apparatus' . Louis Althusser has proposed a materialistic conception of ideology, which made use of the special type of discourse. He analysed the concept of the ideological State Apparatus to explain his theory of ideology. Another movement in the history was 'Feminism movement', which has concerted on women living on equal terms with men. The word feminism as a synonym was used for 'femininity' in 19th century. The feminist waves are four waves. They are the First-wave feminism, which lasted from the 18th century until World War 11 and centred on the basic civil rights, such as the right to vote and to own property.

The Second- wave feminism, which lasted from the end of World War 11 until the defeat of the Equal Rights Amendment in the 1980s and centered on achieving equality in the workplace and protecting reproductive choice. The Third- wave feminism incorporates the racial justice, LGBT rights, and class oppression into the feminist worldview and seeks real, practical, equality for all women. The recent one is the Fourth- wave feminism is a feminist movement that began around the early 2010s and is characterised by a focus on the empowerment of women, the use of internet tools and equality by focusing on gendered norms and the marginalisation of women in society. On interesting tradition is Gynocriticism, which is the historical study of women writers as a distinct literary tradition. Elaine Showalter has coined this term in her essay " Toward a Feminist Poetics". This is one of the best books, that refers to a criticism that constructs a female framework for the analysis of women's literature, to

develop new models based on the study of female experience, rather than to adapt male models and theories Virginia Woolf and Simon de Beauvoir. Intersexuality is another term derived from the Latin *intertexto*, meaning to intermingle while weaving, intertextuality is a term first introduced by French semiotician Julia Kristeva in the late sixties. Magic realism style or magical realism is an aesthetic style or genre of fiction in which magical elements blend to create a realistic atmosphere that accesses a deeper understanding of reality. Eurocentrism refers to a discursive tendency to interpret the histories and cultures of non - European societies from a European perspective. Common features of Eurocentric thought include. Negritude is the self- affirmation of black people. The concept of Negritude emerged as an expression of a revolt against the historical situation of a French colonialism and racism, one of the most popular is Sedar Senghor from Senegal. In the late 1920s.

Orientalism is a style of thought based upon ontological and epistemological distinction made between the orient and the occident. According to Edward W. Said, the West has created a dichotomy between the reality of the East and the romantic notion of the orient . Ecocriticism focuses on the underlying ecological values. Ecocritics investigate such things as the underlying ecological values, by the word nature, and whether the examination of place should be a distinctive category, much like class, gender or race. William Rueckert was the first person to use the term ecocriticism in 1978. The final one I would like to discuss 'Queer theory', which is a set of ideas based around the idea that identities are not fixed and do not determine who we are.

Conclusion

Some of the important periodicals in the history are 'The Times Literary Supplement, The New York Times Book Review, London Review of Books, The Nation and The New Yorker. By studying ' Literary criticism' the readers will understand the literary texts in the best way. Literary texts play a vital role to unfold a wide scope to comprehend the different dimensions of literatures in the world. Behind the texts, culture, traditions, historicity and other important themes are hidden, which are detailedly discussed in Literary texts.

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